

POLYMER-DERIVED FIBER-REINFORCED CERAMIC MATRIX COMPOSITES AND CMCs PRODUCED BY POWDER PROCESSING: STATE OF THE ART AND FUTURE ASPECTS

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ABSTRACT

A critical review of the production of continuous fiber-reinforced CMCs is given under the aspects of composite homogeneity, density and porosity. Thermal and chemical stability of available fibers is discussed with regard to the different processing routes. Tailoring of the fiber/matrix interface and the possibility of improving the oxidation resistance are shown by optimizing the materials and technological parameters. The potential of combining various processing techniques is pointed out.

INTRODUCTION

Continuous fiber reinforced ceramic matrix composites can be produced by various powder routes (hot-pressing, hot-isostatic pressing, reaction bonding) as well as by powder-free processing (chemical vapor, metal melt or liquid precursor infiltration). Low temperature processing is a decisive factor for the successful fabrication of fiber composites since oxide and non-oxide fibers available at present tend to lose their strength between 1000 and 1300 °C.

Other critical points are the homogeneity of the composites, this means the homogeneous distribution of the fibers, and the stability of the fiber/matrix interface. Based on the state of the art at present it is no problem to infiltrate preforms of high fiber content homogeneously with liquids or gases. In contrast, the homogeneous surrounding of fibers with powder particles is connected mainly with two problems: the preparation of submicron powders, and the homogenous surrounding of fibers with powder particles.

It is well known that the mechanical properties of composites are controlled by the properties of the fiber/matrix interface. However, till now the insufficient experimental data do not allow quantitative predictions of the correlation: technological parameters \Leftrightarrow interface characteristics \Leftrightarrow properties of composite. Generally, a weak fiber/matrix bonding is preferable to achieve high toughness and strain-to-failure values. Thus, the individual characteristics of the interface have to be optimized for each fiber-matrix system.

In this work, some essential problem areas for powder and powder-free processing techniques will be discussed: homogeneity of composites as well as stability of fibers and interface characteristics during processing. Moreover, future aspects regarding optimization and combination of different techniques are pointed out.

FABRICATION OF CMCs

Powder Processing (Hot Pressing, Hot Isostatic Pressing)

Powder processing is characterized by preparing fine powders, packing of powder particles around the fibers and pressure-assisted sintering (Fig.1, left side). Mostly, the two routes, hot pressing and reaction bonding, are used to produce CMCs. During hot pressing 3-7 layers of uniaxially aligned fibers incorporated in the ceramic powder were stacked up and sintered under a pressure of 35-40 MPa at temperatures of 1500-1800 °C [1].

Singh [1] used, for example, hot pressing between 1500 and 1600 °C to produce zircon ($ZrSiO_4$) matrix composites uniaxially reinforced with SiC fibers (SCS-6, as-received and additionally BN-coated). The composites exhibited a small amount of porosity < 1%, however, the stress-strain behavior was comparable to monolithic zircon. Nakano and Kamiya produced C/Si₃N₄ and C/Sialon composites by combination of powder method and chemical route followed by hot pressing at 1700 °C in argon atmosphere [2]. The resulting composites exhibited a high flexural strength of about 500 MPa.

As a consequence, hot pressing allows to produce dense materials with good oxidation resistance, but the high processing temperature and the matrix shrinkage lead to fiber damage.

Figure 1. Processing routes for ceramic matrix composites

Reaction Bonding

In contrast, reaction bonding overcomes some of these problems and offers additionally several advantages. First, the nitridation temperature is relatively low (1160-1400 °C), second, no shrinkage occurs and no additives are necessary. The main disadvantage of this process is the residual porosity of 12-15 % which limits the oxidation resistance of RBSN materials.

The investigations of Bhatt [3] in the field of SiC-fiber-reinforced RBSN showed the potential of these materials with essentially improved stress-strain behavior. At room temperature the ultimate tensile strength of about 700 MPa was measured. Many investigations have been performed to optimize the technological process, and thus, to prevent the degradation of fibers. Bhatt used the low temperature nitridation procedure (1200 °C, 40 h). The SiC/RBSN composites produced via low temperature nitridation exhibited a favorable stress-strain behavior.

Omatete et al. [4] developed SiC/RBSN composites combining two processes: the formation of the Si powder bodies by gel casting and reaction bonding in a microwave furnace at 1250 °C for 8h or at 1350 °C for 4h. The composites sintered at lower temperature showed significant fiber pull-out. However, those materials sintered at higher temperature exhibited only limited fiber pull-out indicating possible fiber degradation and strong matrix/fiber bonding which is not desirable. The SiC/RBSN composite sintered at low temperatures still contains elemental silicon, thus, the high temperature properties may become worse. The use of fine powders is very profitable due to the reduction of nitridation time and/or temperature. Additionally, the use of very small particles permits very good packing of the powder particles around the fibers which improved the homogeneity of composites [5]. The reaction bonding technique was also successfully used for the production of composites with Al₂O₃ matrix. The Al₂O₃ fiber preforms were infiltrated with an Al/Al₂O₃ submicron slurry and subsequently oxidized at a temperature of 1250°C for 30 minutes [6].

Powder-Free Processing

Powder-free processing is characterized by building up a fiber preform, which defines an open pore structure, infiltration and pyrolysis of gases (CVI: Chemical Vapor Infiltration) or liquid (LOIP: Liquid Oligomer Infiltration Pyrolysis) preceramic compounds (precursors) and a gradual densification process (Fig. 1, right side). Using these techniques, complex shaped parts with homogenous matrices can be manufactured, realizing a large variation of fiber volume contents (10-70 %, short or endless fibers). Both methods use relatively low temperatures (CVI: 900-1200 °C, LOIP: 700-1100 °C), thus, no fiber degradation occurs thermally. Nevertheless, the long infiltration times (CVI) and the need of repeating infiltration/pyrolysis (LOIP), because of the high shrinkage which results from the volume change liquid precursor ⇒ solid ceramic (1.0 ⇒ 2.0-3.4 gcm⁻³), make both processes time consuming, which may be the main disadvantage at present.

For CVI processing [7] molecular precursors are available for different matrices (e.g. SiC, Si₃N₄, B₄C, BN, TiB₂). Research was mainly concentrated on optimizing processing parameters and understanding the infiltration process (reduce processing time, obtain homogenous infiltration). To avoid strong bonding and chemical attack the fibers are often coated as a first step in the CVI process.

For the pyrolysis of oligomeric compounds (LOIP) precursors with various chemical compositions (carbides and nitrides of e.g. B, Al, Si, Ti, Ta) have been developed. In order to meet the requirements of various techniques (fiber spinning, coating, infiltration) viscosity, curing conditions and ceramic yield have been optimized by precursor chemistry [8, 9]. With respect to the infiltration process of fiber preforms one essential result of our investigations in the Si-C-N system is that all precursors are liquid without using a solvent. The reactivity of the precursors (stability, curing temperature) is controlled by the type of functional groups in the silazane chain. Intra- and intermolecular mixtures of vinylic- and Si-H-substituents are responsible for high ceramic yields [10]. As a consequence, fiber-reinforced composites with various C/N ratios in the matrix have been produced with few infiltration/pyrolysis cycles. Besides optimizing precursor chemistry, the high volume shrinkage may be overcome using dispersions of precursors with passive [11] or active [12] fillers.

At the end of both processes some porosity, of about 6-15 % for CVI and down to < 2 % (adjustable) for LOIP, still remains. Thus, further oxidation protection has to be established as it is necessary after reaction bonding.

FIBER STABILITY

For keeping the thermal and chemical stability of the fibers and their coatings the CMC processing techniques have to fulfill various requirements. During processing the fibers should

preserve their good mechanical properties, and the desired weak bonding to the matrix should not be affected.

Commercially available carbon and silicon carbide fibers are mostly used. Carbon fibers are the only ones which are stable up to 2000 °C. No degradation (crystallization, decomposition) is expected in inert gas atmosphere. Oxidation in air starts at about 600 °C, above this temperature further protection is necessary.

Non-oxide fibers are passivated through an oxide layer and are stable up to 1200 °C. During heat treatment of SiC Nicalon fibers at temperatures above 1250°C the fiber nanostructure changes due to the reaction of amorphous phase $\text{SiO}_{1.09}\text{C}_{0.45}$ with free carbon. As a result of this reaction, the SiC content increases and the mass of the fiber decreases which causes degradation of the fibers [13]. A drastic decrease of the mechanical strength is observed at temperatures higher than 1200 °C.

Because of the limited thermal fiber stability the application of processing routes, which include temperatures > 1200 °C has to be avoided. Furthermore, the use of composites has to be limited to $T < 1200$ °C.

Actually developed SiC Hi-Nicalon fibers are more crystalline and exhibit only 0.5 mass-% oxygen. It may be expected that the Hi-Nicalon fibers will be more stable. New development lines of non-oxide fibers result in fully crystalline fibers (SiC, CARBORUNDUM LTD) or in amorphous fibers (Si-B-N, BAYER AG) to improve both, the thermal stability during processing and the maximum application temperature (long-term stability).

Chemical attack of the fibers and/or coatings due to reactions with the matrix and/or atmosphere during processing is discussed in the following chapter in terms of interface stability.

INTERFACE FIBER/MATRIX

Toughness and strain-to-failure of CMCs are controlled by the nature and properties of the interface fiber/matrix. The characteristics of the interface are determined by the inside and the environmental stability of the composite constituents as well as by the mechanical and chemical compatibility between fiber and matrix. Thus, the internal stability of all constituents should be assured during processing and at the expected application temperatures. At higher temperatures the composite constituents can decompose either inherently or because of the presence of impurities. The environmental effects can be divided into two categories. The first is the reaction of fibers with the atmosphere during processing, the second is caused by oxidation of the composite constituents at application conditions.

Carbon and SiC fibers are mostly used as reinforcements because of their high modulus, high strength and their availability. The number of fiber/matrix systems which may be selected is limited by thermal stresses induced by differences in thermal expansion between the fiber and the matrix. Si_3N_4 , SiC and mullite ($3\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{SiO}_2$) show relatively low thermal expansion coefficients, thus, make these materials suitable for the production of CMC matrices. In addition, Si_3N_4 and SiC can be produced by low temperature processing as reaction bonding, chemical vapor infiltration and infiltration/pyrolysis of liquid oligomers.

The chemical compatibility between fibers and processing atmosphere as well as between fibers and matrix should be guaranteed under processing and application conditions. An example for the first case is the incorporation of SCS-6 fibers in RBSN. It is well known that the H_2 content in the nitridation atmosphere promotes the nitridation process of Si-powders, however, damage of fibers was observed [3]. Our investigations [14] showed that the $\text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2$ atmosphere can be used during nitridation, but the temperature range in which the $\text{N}_2 + \text{H}_2$ atmosphere is used has to be optimized under the aspect of fiber stability.

Moreover, even a slight reaction might create a strong bonding between matrix and the reinforcing component, which is not desirable. Consequently, a fiber coating is needed to overcome this problem, to modify frictional forces at the fiber/matrix interface as well as to im-

prove the damage tolerance of the composite via fiber pull-out. If a coating is required only those combinations of CMC constituents can be used which do not react with each other. The most common coatings are C, BN and SiC. Small molecules (CH_4 , BF_3/NH_3 , $\text{CH}_3\text{SiCl}_3/\text{H}_2$, respectively) are decomposed on the fiber surface to build up films of about $0.05\text{--}3\ \mu\text{m}$ thickness at temperatures of $900\text{--}1200\ ^\circ\text{C}$. The use of carbon in combination with oxides and nitrides may cause carbothermic reduction. Most commonly SiC/C and SiC/BN combinations are used.

Singh and Brun examined BN coatings on SiC and mullite fibers in a mullite matrix. The BN-coated SiC fibers caused a much weaker bonding with mullite than the uncoated fibers. The BN coating prevented the fiber-matrix reaction in the mullite/mullite composite (but in this case the fibers degraded during processing because of the high processing temperature).

In our own investigations with the SiC-SCS-6/RBSN composites three different types of fracture behavior were observed during push-out test: first, debonding took place between fiber coating and matrix (Fig. 2a), second, debonding occurred between the different layers of the coating (duplex behavior, Fig. 2b), and third, the coating was kept in the matrix, whereas the fiber was pushed-out without coating (Fig. 2c). Such a behavior of fibers can be controlled by materials and technological parameters.

Figure 2. Variation of the debonding behavior of SiC(SCS6)-fiber reinforced RBSN during push-out tests

- a) Debonding between fiber and coating
- b) Debonding between different layers of the coating ("duplex")
- c) Debonding between matrix and coating

Debonding between the outer carbon layer and the RBSN matrix was observed in composites with very weak bonding, caused by a coarse silicon starting powder. 70 % of specimens with additives $\text{Y}_2\text{O}_3 + \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ exhibited the duplex behavior of the fibers. The third type of debonding was observed in composites with a high content of elemental silicon after the nitridation process [14]. As a result, the mechanical properties of the interface fiber/matrix could be controlled in this system by various materials and technological parameters. The shear strength of the interface fiber/matrix could be varied over a wide range between 5.6 and 18.0 MPa by changing the mean particle size of the Si powders as well as by changes in chemical composition of the RBSN matrix (additives, impurities) and in the nitridation atmosphere [15].

As a conclusion, it may be stated that the chemical stability of fibers and fiber coating compounds, the interfacial characteristics, and consequently the debonding and stress-strain behavior can be controlled and adjusted by various materials and processing parameters as well as by suitable coatings. The effectiveness of these variables is strongly dependent on the composite system and the type of processing.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES AND OXIDATION BEHAVIOR

Continuous fiber reinforced CMCs are at different stages of development. Only a few fiber/matrix systems have been developed to the stage which permits to measure the macroscopic properties of composites (Table 1). These are mainly C/SiC, SiC/SiC, SiC/RBSN, SiC/ZrSiO₄. From the first two groups of composites large and complex-shaped components have been produced [11, 16, 17, 18].

Table 1 Mechanical Properties of CMCs from Different Processing Routes (*: σ_{bending})

system	Powder Routes		Powder Free Processing				
	SiC/ RBSN [3]	SiC / ZrSiO ₄ [11]	SiC / SiC [15]	SiC / SiC [11]	C / SiC [15]	C / SiC [11]	C / SiCN [16]
processing	RB	HP	CVI	LOIP	CVI	LOIP	LOIP
σ_{tensile} , MPa	692±150	681±36	280-340	160	270-330	230-260	200-250*
ϵ , %	0.6	-	0.5-0.8	0.45	0.7-0.9	0.5-0.6	> 3.0
E, GPa	193±7	235±266	180-220	-	90-100	80-90	60-100

The composites with oxide matrix show, naturally, very good oxidation resistance. The oxidation behavior of composites with RBSN, CVI (SiC) or LOIP (SiC/Si₃N₄) matrix is limited due to the open porosity. In the latter cases, the combination of various processing techniques leads to an improved resistance. For example, in our work infiltration experiments of RBSN materials with liquid polysilazane were performed. This reduces the open porosity, the diameter of the pores and diminishes the oxidation rate of RBSN (Fig. 3). No fiber damage was observed due to the low pyrolysis temperature of the organometallics (< 1000 °C). In the case of LOIP-based matrices, further siliconization results in a dense composite with no significant mass change up to 1500 °C (Fig. 4).

Figure 3. Post-densification of RBSN materials through infiltration with polysilazane followed by pyrolysis

a) Decrease of open porosity and pore radius b) Improvement of oxidation resistance

Figure 4. Oxidation stability of C-fiber-reinforced Si-C-N before (1) and after (2) siliconization

FUTURE ASPECTS AND DEVELOPMENT LINES

None of the above mentioned processing techniques meets all the requirements of a desired CMC, e.g. homogenous and relatively dense matrix, no fiber damage, and pseudoplastic fracture behavior. To avoid fiber damage the processing parameters have to be carefully adjusted. Hot pressing seems not a reasonable way because thermally stable fibers in the needed temperature range (1500-1800 °C) are not available till now. Additionally, fibers are damaged mechanically during the hot-pressing step.

Most promising routes are infiltration techniques and reaction bonding. CVI-SiC and RBSN give homogenous matrices and high strength values. In order to achieve damage tolerance, the interface has to be optimized, too. In the case of reaction bonding, besides fiber coating, particle size and packing as well as additives are suitable measures to form a weak interface, as demonstrated with our own investigations. For CVI processing coating of the fibers is the central point. To achieve the "duplex" behavior more than one layer may be necessary.

The advantages of the LOIP method are low manufacturing costs, easy variation of the constituting elements, low processing temperatures, a homogenous matrix and near-net-shape processing. The mechanical strength values limited till now may be overcome by changing from amorphous (density 1.8-2.5 gcm⁻³) to more crystalline matrices (density about 3.1-3.4 gcm⁻³), and using the in-situ strengthening of nanostructured particles by subsequent crystallization treatment (nanocomposites, hybride materials). A weak interface, as it was found in the fiber/matrix compound C/SiCN, may be achieved for other systems by optimizing precursor chemistry without the necessity of further fiber coating. The number of infiltration/pyrolysis cycles can be reduced by winding or laminating of fibers coated with dispersions of precursors and passive [11] or active [12] fillers. All precursors should be stable in air to reduce the fabrication costs.

In order to fulfill all the requirements mentioned above, the combination of different processing techniques is proposed. Further strengthening of porous ceramics may be reached by the LOIP method, oxidation resistance may be increased by siliconization. For high temperature applications and cyclic loading each of the CMC components (fiber/interface/matrix) must be stable for itself.

The critical point here is the still limited thermal stability of the fibers. Fibers from Si-B-N, which retain the amorphous state up to high temperatures, as well as sintered fibers (grain size about 2 µm) of SiC are still in the development phase. Lower creep rates of these fibers

are rather expected than from conventional fibers. In this respect great efforts are undertaken to reduce the oxygen content to an absolute minimum. The successful development in this direction would have consequences for the processing routes (processing temperature) and the temperature range of application.

Based on the development of non-oxide based composites, the experiences from reaction bonding and the LOIP method can be transferred to oxide/oxide composites for high temperature applications. The prerequisite for this development is, however, the successful development of high-temperature stable, creep resistant oxide fibers.

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